

of the yams of *Dioscorea* plants (Family: Dioscoreaceae) and was first isolated from *Dioscorea tokoro* Makino³⁻⁴ of Japan and later Marker and his collaborators³⁵ isolated it from a number of Mexican *Dioscorea* plants.

The *Dioscorea* plants are climbers. The plants have often prickly stems. The leaves are reticulate and petiole is often angled. Flowers are small, unisexual, dioecious or monoecious in separate spikes. The yams (tubers) of these plants vary from species to species as regards size and shape. Generally the tubers are soft with white flesh, although there are others with hard woody tubers. The edible varieties are used as cheap substitutes for potatoes. Sometimes inedible tubers are also taken by Santhals, Kols, and hill tribes in our country after proper processing to remove poisonous constituents like alkaloids and saponins. The method used generally is a thorough washing of the sliced or macerated tubers with hot water. The product after drying is usually obtained as a white powder which is used like flour.

Notable poisonous yams amongst the Indian *Dioscorea* plants are those of *D. hispida*, *D. deltoidea*, and *D. prazeri*. *D. hispida* is known in Western India as *marapashpoli* or deadly strangle cake on account of its poisonous character. The Bhils poison tigers by placing pounded tubers on the carcasses of kills. *D. prazeri* is called *Kenchong* by the Lepchas and *kukur torul* or dog's yam by the Paharias. Indian names of *D. deltoidea* are *kins*, *kildri*, *kithi*, *krithi*, *krits*, *krish*, etc. Both *D. prazeri* and *D. deltoidea* are used as soap, specially for washing wool and silk also for washing hair to remove lice, and as fish poisons for catching fish. Some of the *Dioscorea* yams are used in the indigenous system of medicine as diuretic.

At least thirty different species of *Dioscorea* plants grow in different parts of this country, some in the hills, others in the plains but mostly in jungles. Some of the edible varieties are even cultivated and yams of these are sold in local markets. Some of the common species are *D. alata*, *D. anguina*, *D. bellocphylla*, *D. daemonia*, *D. bulbifera*, *D. deltoidea*, *D. glabra*, *D. hispida*, *D. Hookeri*, *D. hamiltonii*, *D. jacquemontii*, *D. kamoensis*, *D. lepcharum*, *D. oppositifolia*, *D. pentaphylla*, *D. prazeri*, *D. pubera*, *D. sativa*, *D. scrotichinii*, *D. tomentosa*, *D. trixerva*, *D. wallichii*, and *D. wattfi*. Yams of twenty different species of these plants were collected mostly through various forest offices and examined in our laboratory. These are: *D. alata*, *D. glabra*, *D. oppositifolia*, *D. wallichii*, *D. bellocphylla*, *D. pubera*, *D. nummularia*, *D. aculeata*, *D. esculenta*, *D. hispida*, *D. pentaphylla*, *D. tomentosa*, *D. prazeri*, *D. bulbifera*, *D. deltoidea*, *D. sativa*, *D. glauca*. Of these, the first eight belong to the right-twining sub-group and the rest to the left-twining sub-group. The last one, *D. glauca*,⁶ although regarded as a variety of *D. nummularia*, is found to have close similarity with *D. prazeri*. Three of the yams could not be identified properly.

The air-dried powdered yams were extracted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°), chloroform, ethyl acetate, and ethanol in an all-glass soxhlet extractor. The solvent-free residue obtained from end fraction was tested for saponin by treatment with water when a comparatively stable froth with characteristic honey-comb structure was produced. Such solutions were subjected to haemolytic test for saponin as also tested for their fish-poison character against gold fish (*Carassius auratus*).

Isolation of the saponin⁷ from the various yams was initially carried out by extracting the air-dried, powdered yams with ethanol followed by defatting the alcoholic extract with ether, hydrolysis with ethanolic hydrochloric acid, and final extraction with ether. Both *D. prazeri* and *D. deltoidea* yielded rather high percentages of extractives.

On account of this and other factors, the extraction of the powdered yams in a soxhlet is associated with considerable difficulties. These were to some extent obviated by carrying out some modifications in the procedure for extraction. It was ultimately possible to further simplify the procedure⁶. For this purpose, the ethanolic extract of the yams after removal of the solvent was treated with sufficient water to produce a colloidal suspension of the saponin. The product was defatted by gentle refluxing of the aqueous suspension with petroleum ether (60-80°), hydrolysed with aqueous hydrochloric acid, and extracted with benzene. Hydrolysis and extraction of diosgenin were carried out in a single stage by gentle refluxing of the defatted product in presence of hydrochloric acid and benzene. The residue obtained from the benzene extract after proper purification gave pure diosgenin. Although Wall and his collaborators⁹ have found it convenient to isolate the saponin from the fresh plant materials, we like to recommend the use of dried powdered yams in the case of isolation of diosgenin from *D. prazeri* and *D. deltoidea*.

More recently, Vishwapal *et al.*¹⁰ claimed a method of isolation of diosgenin from *Dioscorea* yams although this method was developed by Rothrock *et al.*¹¹ earlier. The method consists in hydrolysing the coarsely powdered, air-dried yams with aqueous hydrochloric acid, washing the product free of acid, drying, and extracting in a soxhlet with petroleum ether (40-60°). This method was described by the American workers as a general procedure for isolation of diosgenin from *Dioscorea* yams, using *D. barbascio* as a typical case and was utilised by Vishwapal *et al.*¹⁰ for isolation of diosgenin, whereas in this laboratory, the same was applied to *D. prazeri*.¹² It may be mentioned in this connection that hydrochloric acid has an adverse effect on diosgenin, since according to Peal¹³ it changes into 25D-spirosta-3, 5-diene when heated with ethanolic hydrochloric acid. In the method developed in this laboratory⁶ in the hydrolytic stage, as soon as any diosgenin is formed it is immediately extracted with benzene and is thus removed from the field of action of hydrochloric acid.

The diosgenin content of the different species of India *Dioscorea* yams has been found to vary noticeably. The average yields of diosgenin from *D. esculenta*, *D. prazeri*, *D. deltoidea*, and *D. glauca* are 0.15-0.2%, 2.5-3.5%, 4-6%, and 4.5-5% respectively. A critical account of the comparative position of *D. deltoidea* and *D. prazeri* with regard to production of diosgenin from Indian resources was published by the present authors.⁶ Although *D. deltoidea* contains a much higher percentage of diosgenin than *D. prazeri*, in various other respects the latter is much more useful. *D. glauca* being very similar to *D. prazeri* has all the advantages of the latter, but in addition the yield of diosgenin is comparable to that of *D. deltoidea*⁶. Moreover, cultivation of *D. glauca*¹⁴ appears to be much more easy. For these reasons *D. glauca* offers a considerable promise as an economic source of diosgenin.

It has been observed, particularly during powdering, that the dust is rather toxic when the yams contain a high percentage of the saponin. It usually causes bad sneezing and produce symptoms similar to catching cold with or without temperature and may even cause gastrointestinal disorder.

The chief constituent of the *Dioscorea* yams is a starchy matter. Tubers of *D. deltoidea* were found to contain 37-38% of starch and *D. prazeri*, 39-40%¹⁵. In view of this it was found desirable to explore the possibility for utilisation of this starchy matter. Most of the starch was found to be present in the thimble after ethanolic extraction of the saponin by the method of Chakravarti *et al.*⁷ and can be utilised for any suitable purpose. In the

method of Rothrock *et al.*¹¹ during hydrolysis of the plant material with aqueous hydrochloric acid, considerable amounts of sugar were, however, found to be formed¹⁵ mostly from the starchy matter and some from the saponin. In this method very little unhydrolysed starch could be found in the plant residues after extraction of diosgenin. In the aqueous hydrochloric acid mother liquor, in addition to the sugars, some amount of laevulinic acid was found to be present, formed obviously by the action of hydrochloric acid on the sugars. By following the improved procedure for preparation of laevulinic acid¹⁶, it was possible to isolate this acid in good yields from the acid liquors after conversion of the remaining sugar into the acid by further heating of the acid liquor.

It has already been stated that hecogenin, another important sapogenin, is present in many *Agave* plants. In this connection an investigation on the sapogenin contents of some local *Agave* plants was carried out. It was found that *Agave cantala* and *Agave sisalana*¹⁷ contain 0.15% and 0.10% hecogenin respectively.

Although the usual method for hydrolysis of the saponin into the sapogenin consists in heating with aqueous hydrochloric acid, the same splitting can be brought about by saponases present in some plants. In the latter case, the hydrolysis may be effected at the room temperature. Considerable amounts of saponases are present in *Agave* leaves due to which hecogenin may be obtained by autolysis. Moreover, *Agave* juice, rich in saponases, can be utilised for hydrolysis of glycosides of other plants. For instance, it has been utilised for isolation of diosgenin from *Dioscorea* tubers¹⁸. This method was tried in this laboratory in the cases of *D. prazeri* and *D. deltoidea*. For this purpose, *D. prazeri* and *D. deltoidea* were separately treated with pressed-out liquor of *Agave cantala* leaves for a definite period. It was then filtered, dried, and extracted with petroleum ether in a soxhlet. The petroleum ether extract after removal of the solvent was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina in each case. The products obtained in the case of *D. deltoidea* were identified as diosgenin and smilagenone and those in the case of *D. prazeri* as diosgenin and epi-smilagenin¹⁹. The formation of smilagenone (IV) and epi-smilagenin (V) under such conditions is quite interesting and in this respect it has been found desirable to make a thorough study of this reaction using only *Dioscorea* yams in the absence of *Agave* juice.

With the above object, fresh yams of *D. prazeri* or *D. deltoidea*, after being cut to pieces and crushed, were kept with excess of water for periods ranging from a few weeks to several months. The product was filtered, dried, and extracted with petroleum ether in a soxhlet. A white crystalline product was obtained, which on chromatography over Brockmann alumina using various mixtures of petroleum ether and benzene furnished

mainly smilagenone (IV), m.p. 188-89° [semicarbazone, m.p. 222-23° (dec.); oxime, m.p. 180° (dec.); 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrozone, m.p. 212-13° (dec.)] and epi-smilagenin (V),²⁰ m.p. 220-22° (acetate, 163-64°, benzoate, 189-90°). The plant residues left after the extraction were hydrolysed with aqueous hydrochloric acid; the hydrolysed product was dried and extracted with petroleum ether. The residue obtained from the latter extract was chromatographed as in the previous cases when only diosgenin could be isolated, the yield varying considerably depending on the period of contract with water and the yields of smilagenone and epi-smilagenin isolated in the previous stage.

When the yams are kept with water for one or two weeks, the yields of smilagenone and epi-smilagenin are low. When the fresh yams (crushed) of *D. prazeri* are kept with water for about three months, the change is almost complete. Further, it is found that longer period of contract with water favours the formation of epi-smilagenin, whereas the shorter period favours the formation of smilagenone. It may be mentioned in this connection that Rothrock *et al.*²¹ reported the isolation of Δ^4 diosgenone in one case of microbiological hydrolysis of *Dioscorea* tubers, although in general, they found that the saponins in *Dioscorea* tubers were cleaved into diosgenin and the sugar moieties by microbiological hydrolysis. Marker *et al.*²², however, reported the formation of diosgenin, smilagenin, and epi-smilagenin from Δ^4 -dehydrotigogenone, administered to a dog on biscuit diet.

To ascertain whether the transformation in the steroid moiety of the saponin takes place in the glycosidic stage or in aglycone stage, experiments were carried out by keeping finely dispersed diosgenin in contact with sufficient amounts of waste liquor, obtained, as stated above, after separation of smilagenone etc. by keeping *Dioscorea* yams in contact with water for about five months. A control specimen consisting of the waste liquor, without addition of any diosgenin, was also kept. After three months both were filtered, dried, and extracted with ether. The residue from the ethereal extract was chromatographed as above, when only unchanged diosgenin could be obtained from the main lot and practically nothing from the control. It is thus evident that the change of the diosgenin moiety of the *Dioscorea* saponin into epi-smilagenin does not take place after the hydrolysis. The fact that only diosgenin, unassociated with any epi-smilagenin, can be obtained from the plant material by hydrolysis with acids after thorough extraction in a soxhlet for epi-smilagenin, as stated above, indicates that the saponin with diosgenin as the aglycone changes into another with epi-smilagenin as the aglycone as a slow reaction and that the newly formed saponin readily hydrolyses into epi-smilagenin and the sugars.

The conversion of diosgenin into pseudodiosgenin constitutes the first step in the preparation of steroid hormones from diosgenin. In this respect it was found desirable to study this conversion properly in this laboratory. The usual method²³ consists in heating the sapogenin with five times its weight of acetic anhydride in a sealed tube at 195-200°. After a number of trials in this laboratory²⁵, the optimum condition for the conversion was found to be a temperature of 192°, the period of heating being ten hours. The reaction could also be carried out conveniently in a glass tube, closed at one end and stoppered tightly by a cork at the other end, immersed in an oil-bath heated to the desired temperature instead of carrying out the reaction in a sealed tube in a bomb furnace. Lastly, as it appeared that pressure had very little effect on this reaction; the conversion was carried out by the present authors²⁵ in an open system using glycerol triacetate (triacetin) as a high-boiling medium. For this purpose, diosgenin was refluxed for 10 hours with acetic anhydride and sufficient amount of glycerol triacetate. The temperature of the liquid mixture was kept at 192° throughout the period. The product, a dark-coloured liquid,

was treated with water when pseudodiosgenin diacetate crystallised out. The product after crystallisation from methanol gave pure pseudodiosgenin diacetate, m.p. 99-100°.

Reference may be made in this connection to the various other modifications carried out in the method of conversion of sapogenins into pseudosapogenins as performed in different laboratories. Marker and Rohrman²⁶ reported the isomerisation of sarsapogenin into pseudosarsapogenin by using various other acid anhydrides, such as, propionic anhydride, succinic anhydride, butyric²⁷ anhydride, in place of acetic anhydride. In the case of butyric²⁷ anhydride (b.p. 198°) the isomerisation was effected by ordinary refluxing. The yields were, however, quite variable and rather low. Good yields of pseudodiosgenin were obtained by Cameron *et al.*²⁷ by heating diosgenin with refluxing octanoic²⁸ acid (b.p. 237°) containing a little acetic anhydride. Amongst other modifications for the conversion of sapogenins (spirostans) to pseudosapogenins (furostenols), mention may be made of Gould *et al.*²⁸ using catalyst like hydrochloric acid, *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, aluminium chloride, etc. under reflux condition and of Dauben and Fonken²⁹, using acetic anhydride containing pyridine hydrochloride for the same conversion.

Our method²⁵ for the conversion of diosgenin to pseudodiosgenin was found to be suitable also for tigogenin which, when mixed with acetic anhydride and sufficient glycerol triacetate, on refluxing at 192° for 10 hrs. gave a dark-coloured liquid. The product on hydrolysis with alcoholic potassium hydroxide yielded pseudotigogenin, m.p. 190-94°. As glycerol triacetate has no catalytic action, it may be replaced by other similar high-boiling solvents.

While studying the chemical properties of diosgenin for its proper utilisation in the preparation of hormones, work was carried out on the action of Raney nickel on diosgenin at different temperatures. For this purpose diosgenin in xylene solution was heated under reflux in presence of Raney nickel catalyst according to the method of Chakravarti and Robinson³⁰ for conversion of strychnine into neostrychnine. On working up, major portion of diosgenin was, however, recovered unchanged. The reaction was then carried out at a higher temperature using *p*-cymene as a solvent instead of xylene. For this purpose, diosgenin, dissolved in freshly distilled *p*-cymene, was mixed with Raney nickel, previously washed with *p*-cymene, and refluxed for twelve hours. The product was filtered. The filtrate was distilled in steam to remove the solvent. The residue thus obtained after separation of water was taken up in ether. The residue from ethereal extract was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina using mixtures of petroleum ether and benzene as eluent, when diosgenone (VI), m.p. 185-86°, was obtained as the major product³¹. On repeating the experiment with excess of Raney nickel, tigogenone (VII), m.p. 206-207°, was obtained. The latter product formed a semicarbazono, m.p. 263° (dec.); oxime, 250-52° (dec.) and 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrozone, m.p. 258° (dec.) and on hydrogenation in glacial acetic acid it yielded dihydrotigogenin, m.p. 166-68°.

The reaction with Raney nickel was also carried out with other steroid sapogenins. Under similar conditions, both smilagenone and epi-smilagenin yielded tigogenone and hecogenin gave hecogenone, m.p. 235-36°. It was also observed that when cholesterol was similarly heated under reflux with Raney nickel in *p*-cymene solution, Δ^4 -cholestenone was the main product. It may be mentioned in this connection that Romo³² reported the formation of 3-oxo- Δ^4 -steroids by oxidation of 3-hydroxy- Δ^4 -steroids with Raney nickel in the presence of acetone or methyl ethyl ketone as hydrogen acceptor, but no reaction occurred with isolated hydroxyl compounds or with 3-hydroxy- Δ^5 -steroids. According to Kleiderer and Kornfeld³³, cholesterol is converted, however, to Δ^4 -cholestenone when cholesterol is heated in toluene solution in presence of cyclohexanone as hydrogen acceptor.

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